

A New Synthesis of All-*trans* Violet Leaf Alcohol Terpenoids. Part IX

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trans-2,6-Noradienol has been synthesised by the modified Wittig reaction with ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate on *trans*-4-hepten-1-al.

The naturally occurring leaf alcohol, isolated from the ethereal oil derived from violet leaves, has been assigned the formulation (I) on the basis of physico-chemical evidence and its synthesis¹. The configuration of the natural isomer is, however, 2-*trans*-6-*cis*-nonadienol¹.

The present communication describes a synthesis of the all-*trans* isomer, which is used in high-grade perfume compositions, along the following lines:

Pent-1-en-3-ol (II), the starting material in the present scheme, was prepared by treatment of vinylmagnesium bromide with propionaldehyde. The compound (II) was converted into its vinyl ether² (III) by mercuric acetate-catalysed *trans*-etherification with ethyl vinyl ether. Subsequent submission of compound (III) to the Claisen rearrangement³ provided *trans*-4-hepten-1-al (IV) in 75% yield.

The aldehyde (IV) was characterised through its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 120°. The IR absorption spectrum showed peaks⁴ at 970 cm^{-1} (*trans*-C=C-), 1720 cm^{-1} (-CHO), 1380 cm^{-1} (C-Me).

1. Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 1561.
2. Vig *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 752.
3. Burgstahler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 4681.
4. Cross, "Introduction to Practical Infrared Spectroscopy", Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1960, pp. 58-63; Church *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 1123.

The aldehyde (IV) was subjected to the modified Wittig's reaction⁵ with ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate when ethyl *trans*-2,6-nonadiene-carboxylate (V) was obtained in 72% yield. Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ester (V) furnished all-*trans*-alcohol (I) in 80% yield.

The compound (I) was characterised through its I R spectrum which showed peaks⁴ at 970cm^{-1} (*trans*-C=C—), 3400 , 1050cm^{-1} (—OH), 1465 , and 1380cm^{-1} (C Me).

*EXPERIMENTAL

Pent-1-en-3-ol (II).—To the Grignard reagent, prepared from vinyl bromide (76.5g.) and magnesium (10.5 g.) in dry THF (100 ml), was added dropwise propionaldehyde (41.5 g.) in THF (70 ml) in the cold. After keeping overnight, the reaction mixture was decomposed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride and worked up in the usual way when the carbinol (II; 16.7 g.) came over at 117° ; yield 40%, n_D^{20} 1.4125. IR spectrum in carbon tetrachloride showed peaks⁴ at 1090cm^{-1} (—OH), 895cm^{-1} ($\begin{matrix} R_1 \\ | \\ R_{11} \end{matrix} \text{C} = \text{CH}_2$), 1380cm^{-1} (C—Me). (Found: C, 75.47; H, 9.43. Calc. for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{O}$: C, 75.35; H, 9.50%).

Pent-1-ene-3-yl vinyl Ether (III).—A solution of the alcohol (II) (16.7 g.) and mercuric acetate (2.14g.) in freshly distilled ethyl vinyl ether (97.1g.) was stirred under reflux in nitrogen atmosphere for 10 hr. The contents were cooled in an ice-bath and stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. with a sodium carbonate solution (10%, 100 ml). The upper layer was separated, dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate, and finally fractionated. The oily fraction boiling at $95\text{--}100^\circ$ was collected and redistilled rapidly over sodium to furnish (III); yield 15.3 g. (46%), n_D^{20} 1.4160. I R spectrum in CCl_4 showed peaks⁴ at 1190cm^{-1} (vinyl ether). (Found: C, 75.05; H, 10.55. Calc. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$: C, 75.0; H, 10.71%).

trans-4-Hepten-1-al (IV).—Vinyl ether (III) (15 g.) was heated for 30 min. at 180° under nitrogen in a fully immersed, half filled, sealed tube. Direct distillation provided 11.25 g. (75%) of the aldehyde (IV) as a colorless oil; b.p. 113° , n_D^{20} 1.4320. IR spectrum showed peaks⁴ at 1720cm^{-1} (—CHO), 970cm^{-1} (*trans* CH=CH—), 1380 , 1470cm^{-1} (C—Me). (Found: C, 75.05; H, 10.55. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ requires C, 75.00; H, 10.71%).

The 2,4-DNP of (IV) was crystallised from ethanol in light orange needles, m.p. 120° . (Found: N, 19.05. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 19.17%).

Ethyl trans-2,6 Nonadiene carboxylate (V).—A slurry of 50% sodium hydride (4.32 g.) was placed in 1,2-dimethoxyethane (100 ml) and ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate (21.53 g.) was added dropwise at the room temperature (20°). After the addition, the solution was stirred until the evolution of gas had ceased. To the resultant yellow solution was then added the aldehyde (IV) (10 g.) slowly and below 0° . After the addition, the solution was further stirred for 1 hr. and then refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The product was extracted with ether after de-

*Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford. IR spectra were recorded on Beckman I. R. 5 with sodium chloride optics, using a thin liquid film and also in CCl_4 solution.

5. Wadsworth *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1733; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, **25**, 680; Bergelson *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 149.

A NEW SYNTHESIS OF ALL-*trans* VIOLET LEAF ALCOHOL TERPENOIDS

composing with large excess of water and then dried (Na_2SO_4). After removal of the solvent, the residue on distillation under reduced pressure furnished the ester (V) (7.2 g.) at $92^\circ/3-4$ mm, yield (72%), n_D^{20} 1.4580. IR spectrum showed peaks⁴ at 1650 , 970 cm^{-1} ($-\text{C}=\text{C}-$), 1720 cm^{-1} (conj. ester), 1380 , 1470 cm^{-1} (C Me). (Found: C, 72.53; H, 7.89. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 72.49; H, 8.0 (%)).

trans-2,6-Nonadienol (I).—To a suspension of LiAlH_4 (0.522 g.) in dry ether (30 ml) was added slowly and with stirring the ester (V) (5 g.) in ether (25 ml) at such a rate as to maintain ether at a gentle reflux. After the mixture had been stirred for further 2hr., the contents were decomposed with a saturated solution of sodium sulphate. The product was extracted with ether, washed with water, and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed and the residue on distillation under vacuum provided the carbinol (I; 4g.) at $58^\circ/2-3$ mm; yield 80%, n_D^{19} 1.4605. (Found: C, 77.14; H, 11.43. Calc. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$: C, 77.18; H, 11.50%).

The identity of the synthetic alcohol (I) was confirmed through its IR absorption spectrum which showed peaks⁴ at 970 cm^{-1} (*trans*- $\text{C}=\text{C}$), 3400 and 1050 cm^{-1} ($-\text{OH}$), 1380 cm^{-1} (C-Me).

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